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Statistical model treatments of nonmetallic elements in water and soil within Nwaebere lake and its environs

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ABSTRACT

Nonmetallic elements found in and around lakes are significant for several reasons, such as their influence on water quality, their potential for resource extraction, and their involvement in geological processes can be sources of pollution and can affect the health of the ecosystem. This study evaluated the distribution, speciation, and potential environmental impact of selected nonmetallic elements in water and surface soils from Nwaebere Lake and adjoining landscapes. Composite water (surface and near-shore) and topsoil samples (0–15 cm) were collected from different sites representing upstream, shoreline, agricultural, and settlement-influenced locations. Concentrations of nitrogen species (nitrate, nitrite, ammonium), total phosphorus (as phosphate), sulphate and chloride were determined using ion chromatography and standard colorimetric methods. Data were analyzed using multivariate techniques (principal component analysis and violin plot) to identify sources and associations. Results showed spatial heterogeneity: nutrient levels (nitrate and phosphate) were significantly higher in sites adjacent to agricultural fields and settlements, indicating inputs from fertilizer runoff and domestic effluents. Elevated sulphate and chloride concentrations near settlement outflows suggested contributions from wastewater and small-scale industrial activities, Multivariate analysis grouped sampling sites by anthropogenic influence and natural geochemical background. study recommends routine monitoring of nutrient and anion loads, implementation of riparian buffer zones, improved waste management in nearby communities, and targeted remediation where nutrient enrichment is greatest. These actions will help protect water quality and ecosystem services provided by Nwaebere Lake.

Keywords: Nonmetallic element, Nwaebere Lake, Principal component analysis, contamination

1. INTRODUCTION

The existence of plants, animals, and human beings relies on water and the nutrients derived from both water and soil [1]. More than 80% of the Earth's surface is made up of water, and it is the second most important element for life after air [2]. Because it creates a habitable ecosystem, water has a major impact on the environment and offers many advantages to people, [3, 4] communities, and the planet. It is the fundamental component of life [5], representing a multifaceted and intricate idea that extends from the individual human cell to the global hydrological cycle [6]. Lakes are classified as aquatic landforms that are located inside continental land surface depressions [7]. They make up around 0.3% of the entire surface water supply, [8] which is mostly used for recreational and human consumption [9], making them an essential part of water resources [10]. Lakes may be created by natural processes or by human activity, the latter coming from mining or ground-excavation-based farming methods [11].

Lakes, which are basic geographic units in land surface ecosystems [12] are essential for the distribution of surface water resources and act as regulators and indicators of regional climate conditions as well as global environmental changes [13, 14]. In the ecological community that consists of "mountains, waters, forests, lakes, grass, and sands," they play a crucial role [15, 16].

The availability of drinking water from rivers and lakes is essential to human survival and advancement, [17] and the quality of these water sources directly affects human health [18]. As a result of recent rapid urbanization and industrialization, a variety of pollutants have contaminated natural water systems through surface runoff and groundwater replenishment, posing an increasing threat to the integrity of these water sources. These pollutants include common pollutants like nitrogen and phosphorus as well as a variety of dangerous substances like heavy metals, antibiotics, and other newly discovered contaminants [19, 20].

Urbanization leads to pollution that adversely affects lakes and diminishes their water quality. The decline in soil and water quality results in reduced water availability [21], which negatively impacts the quality of water for agricultural use, human consumption, and livestock. This situation poses significant risks to both human and animal health, while also threatening food security. The health of individuals relies on various minerals found in water, such as salt, potassium, and chlorine [22, 23]. Consuming water rich in these minerals can provide numerous benefits, including stronger teeth and healthier skin [24]. Therefore, it is essential to ensure access to clear, pure water that contains the appropriate levels of minerals [25].

Maintaining high drinking water standards is essential to protecting public health because the quality of drinking water has a significant impact on human health [26, 27], as well as the incidence of infections and diseases [28]. According to reports from around the world, a variety of human activities have contaminated water sources [29, 30]. All levels of the ecosystem are negatively impacted when pollution causes a lake's water quality to decline. The health of organisms at the base of the food chain is also impacted by this degradation, in addition to humans and higher animals.

Lakes and ponds hold water for longer periods of time than flowing bodies of water like streams, [31] which allows physical, chemical, and biological factors to interact and cause changes in the quality of the water [32]. The substantial anthropogenic activities in the Lake Nwaebere region, including agriculture, livestock rearing, and residential developments [33, 34], have a negative influence on the overall quality of the lake, as evidenced by the soil and lake water quality [35-37].

Figure 1. Map of study location.

2. STUDY LOCATION

The lake represents a typical lowland inland valley characterized by a series of distinctive floodplain regions that are crucial for nature conservation. This wetland is situated in the center of Owerri. Consequently, all runoff waters are directed into the wetland, which is a significant focus of this study, as this may lead to the introduction of contaminants into both the wetland and the groundwater sources. The floodplain regions primarily consist of seasonally flooded grasslands and reedbed habitats. It is located in the upper course of the river and traverses some agricultural lands that are managed with relative intensity before reaching the designated area. The primary channel of Lake Nwaebere has undergone substantial modifications and has been partially straightened to facilitate land drainage. Additionally, there are several water bodies that are directly connected to the main river, along with multiple drainage channels within the floodplain.

2. 1. Sample collection

Water sample collection

Water samples were collected at five different points of the lake as shown in Figure 1, using well labelled five sample containers (plastic bottles) for physical and chemical analysis during rainy and dry seasons.

Soil sample

Soil samples were collected with the use of cleaned plastic trowel at five different points of the wetland using well labelled five polyethene bags during rainy and dry seasons.

3. PREPARATION OF MATERIALS

Digestion

A crucible with 2g of the soil sample was weighed and then placed in a muffle furnace for ashing at a temperature of 4500 °C for 2 hours. After ashing, the sample was taken out of the furnace and allowed to cool. The dry ash obtained was placed into a 250 ml beaker, and subsequently, 20 ml of 20% H₂SO₄ was introduced. This mixture was then heated in a water bath for 20 minutes, filtered, and adjusted to a final volume of 50 ml with distilled water before being stored in a sample bottle for AAS analysis of macro and micronutrients [38].

Preparation of Reference Solution

A collection of standard metal solutions was developed within the ideal concentration range. The reference solutions were generated daily by diluting individual stock element solutions with water that contained 1.5 ml of concentrated nitric acid per liter. A calibration blank was created using all reagents, excluding the metal stock solutions. For each metal, a calibration curve was established by graphing the absorbance of the standards against their respective concentrations [39].

Chloride Determination

Procedure: A 100 ml aliquot of the clear 10% sample was transferred into an Erlenmeyer flask, and the pH was adjusted to a range of 7-10 using either H₂SO₄ or NaOH solution. Subsequently, a 100 ml of K₂CrO₄ indicator solution was introduced, resulting in a consistent reddish-brown coloration with the standard AgNO₃ solution. The AgNO₃ titrant underwent standardization, and a reagent blank was created. Typically, a blank volume of 0.2-0.3 ml is standard for this method [40].

Calculation

$$\text{Chloride Ion Concentration } \left(\frac{\text{mg}}{\text{L}} \right) = \frac{N \times V \times 35.5 \times 1000}{\text{Volume of sample (mL)}}$$

Phosphate Determination

Procedure: Exactly 100 ml of the homogenized and filtered sample was pipetted into a conical flask. The same volume of distilled water (serving as control) was also pipetted into another conical flask. 1ml of 18M H₂SO₄ and 0.89g of ammonium persulphate were added to both conical flasks and gently boiled for 1 ½ hours, keeping the volume of 25-50 cm³ with distilled water. It was then cooled; one drop of phenolphthalein indicator was added and after neutralized to a faint pink colour with the 2M NaOH solution. The pink colour was discharged by drop wise addition of 2M HCl, and the solution made up to 100 ml with distilled water. For the colorimetric analysis, 20 ml of the sample was pipetted into test tubes, followed by the addition of 10 ml of the combined reagent. The mixture was shaken and allowed to stand for 10 minutes prior to measuring the absorbance at 690 nm using a spectrophotometer, with 20 ml of distilled water and 1 ml of the reagent serving as the reference [41, 42].

Methods for Calibration

Standard phosphate solution: A total of 219.5 mg of dried analytical reagent-grade potassium hydrogen phosphate was dissolved in distilled water and adjusted to a final volume of 1000 ml, yielding a concentration of 1 ml = 50.0 µg of phosphate. A 10 ml aliquot of this stock solution was further diluted to 1000 ml, yielding a concentration of 1 ml = 0.05 mg. Calibration standards with concentrations ranging from 0 (blank) to 0.05 mg/L, at intervals of 0.01 mg, were prepared by diluting the stock solution with distilled water.

$$\text{Conc of sample} = \frac{\text{Abs of sample} \times \text{conc of std}}{\text{Abs of std}}$$

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Nitrate Determination

Procedure: A precise volume of 50 ml of the digested sample was transferred into a porcelain dish and subjected to evaporation until dry on a hot water bath. Subsequently, 2 ml of phenol disulphonic acid was introduced to the residue, which was continuously stirred with a glass rod to ensure dissolution. An alkaline solution was prepared by adding concentrated sodium hydroxide and distilled water while stirring. This mixture was then filtered into a Nessler's tube and adjusted to a final volume of 50 ml with distilled water. Following the development of color, the absorbance was measured at 410 nm using a spectrophotometer [43]. A standard graph was constructed with concentration plotted on the X-axis and the spectrophotometric readings (absorbance) on the Y-axis. The nitrate concentration was determined by comparing the absorbance of the sample against the standard curve, with results expressed in mg/L.

$$\text{Conc of sample} = \frac{\text{Abs of sample} \times \text{Conc of std}}{\text{Abs of std}}$$

4. RESULTS AND DISSCUSION

The concentrations of nonmetallic minerals element of water sample from Lake Nwaebere and soil in the adjacent areas during both seasons are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Phosphate

Tables 1 present the concentrations in mg of nonmetallic mineral composition of Lake Nwaebere during both dry and rainy seasons while the nonmetallic minerals element of soil samples from Lake Nwaebere during dry season and rainy seasons are presented in Table 2. The average phosphate concentration in the lake was measured at 10.577 mg/L in the dry season and 9.21 mg/L in the rainy season. It is noteworthy that phosphate levels were higher in the dry season compared to the rainy season, although both values remain below the World Health Organization's threshold of 50 mg/L. In the wetland soil, the average phosphate concentrations were 6.43 mg/L during the dry season and 16.40 mg/L in the rainy season. It was observed that phosphate levels in the soil increased during the rainy season, likely due to mineral leaching

from rainfall [44]. Furthermore, agricultural activities along the lake's banks may also contribute to heightened phosphate levels in the wetland, particularly during the rainy season when such practices are more common.

Sulphate

Tables 1 and 2 provide an overview of the sulphate levels observed in water in Lake Nwaebere and the adjacent wetland soil across both dry and rainy seasons. The findings reveal that the average sulphate concentration in the lake water was 120.598 mg/L during the dry season, while it decreased to 84.67 mg/L in the rainy season. It is noteworthy that the sulphate concentration in the lake water samples was greater during the dry season than in the rainy season, although both values fall within the acceptable limits set by the World Health Organization. In terms of wetland soil, the average sulphate concentrations were recorded at 195.56 mg/L in the dry season and 156.4 mg/L in the rainy season. Sulphate ions are typically present in natural water systems, with many sulphate compounds exhibiting high solubility [45, 46].

Chloride

The concentrations of chloride in Lake Nwaebere and the nearby wetland soils were assessed during both the wet and dry seasons. The recorded chloride levels for the dry and rainy seasons were 26.0 mg/L and 78.0 mg/L for the lake water, and 41.2 mg/L and 147.4 mg/L for the wetland soils, respectively. It is noteworthy that the chloride levels in the lake water were higher during the rainy season for both the lake and the wetland soils. This suggests an increased accumulation of chloride ions in these regions, likely resulting from runoff from various catchment areas that feed into the lake, which is influenced by leaching from diverse environments. Chlorides are present in natural water bodies at varying concentrations, shaped by geographical factors [47]. They can enter surface waters from numerous sources, including chloride-rich rocks, agricultural runoffs, industrial discharges, oil well effluents [48], and wastewater treatment plant outputs. Although trace quantities of chlorides are essential for the proper cellular functions of both plant and animal life [49].

Nitrate

Nitrate concentrations in Lake Nwaebere and the adjacent wetland soils were evaluated during both the wet and dry seasons. The nitrate levels for the dry and rainy seasons were 1.117 mg/L and 7.55 mg/L for the lake water, and 10.09 mg/L and 11.7 mg/L for the wetland soils, respectively. Nitrates are essential nutrients required for the development of plants, which also encompasses algae. When present in excess, they promote rapid algal proliferation, resulting in unsightly and potentially harmful blooms. Furthermore, this may result in a reduction of oxygen levels, as the breakdown of algae utilizes dissolved oxygen present in the water, leading to conditions of hypoxia or anoxia [50], (characterized by low or absent oxygen). Such circumstances can stifle fish and various aquatic life forms. Also, reduced biodiversity may occur, as the altered water conditions can adversely affect the diversity and abundance of aquatic species [51], favoring certain tolerant species while negatively impacting others. Elevated nitrate levels in lakes can result in eutrophication, which leads to excessive growth of algae and plants, oxygen depletion, and detrimental effects on aquatic life [52, 53]. Moreover, high nitrate concentrations can pose health risks to both humans and animals. Elevated nitrate

levels in drinking water can lead to methemoglobinemia [54], (commonly referred to as blue baby syndrome) in infants, a condition that impairs the blood's ability to transport oxygen. Some studies have suggested potential associations between nitrate exposure and other health issues, such as diabetes and infectious disorders; however, further research is required to validate these connections [55, 56].

Table 1. Nonmetallic Minerals element of Lake Nwaebere (water).

	Dry season (mg/L)				Rainy season (mg/L)			
Sample	Cl ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	NO ₃ ⁻	PO ₄ ³⁻	Cl ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	NO ₃ ⁻	PO ₄ ³⁻
A	30	153.593	1.20357	20.47	76	67.208	8.261	10.803
B	40	124.551	1.61961	5.671	89	119.156	6.957	6.321
C	20	22.7545	0.78752	2.517	72	71.104	6.923	7.358
D	20	124.252	0.95097	2.886	70	68.831	7.324	9.298
E	20	177.844	1.02526	21.342	83	97.078	8.328	12.274
Mean	26	120.598	1.117	10.577	78	84.67	7.55	9.21
SD	8.94	59.1	0.318	9.512	7.9	22.82	0.69	2.43
WHO	250	500	50	50	250	500	50	50

Table 2. Dry season nonmetallic mineral element of the soil around Lake Nwaebere.

	Dry season (mg/L)				Rainy season (mg/L)			
Sample	Cl ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	NO ₃ ⁻	PO ₄ ³⁻	Cl ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	NO ₃ ⁻	PO ₄ ³⁻
A	40	219.761	14.279	6.611	167	119.156	14.950	18.963
B	38	120.359	6.523	6.242	145	219.805	10.301	15.017
C	42	185.629	14.339	7.617	142	131.818	7.592	9.298
D	52	238.024	8.796	5.235	139	158.766	10.669	15.585
E	34	214.072	6.508	6.443	144	152.273	15.017	23.177
Mean	41.2	195.56	10.09	6.43	147.4	156.4	11.7	16.4
SD	6.7	46.05	3.96	0.852	11.193	38.84	3.21	5.135

PCA PLOT

Figure 2. PCA plot for water during dry season.

Figure 3. PCA plot for water during rainy season.

The vectors for the PCA Plot for water during the dry season between Cl^- and NO_3^- showed positive correlation, while that between PO_4^{3-} and (Cl^- and NO_3^-) are likely not correlated. Whereas there appeared to be negative correlations between PO_4^{3-} and (SO_4^{2-}).

Figure 4. PCA plot for soil during dry season.

Figure 5. PCA plot for soil during rainy season.

However, for the rainy season Cl^- and PO_4^{3-} showed strong positive correlation while here appeared to be no correlation between NO_3^- and (Cl^- and PO_4^{3-}) and also no correlation between SO_4^{2-} and (Cl^- and PO_4^{3-}), as shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3. For the vectors for the PCA Plot for soil during the dry season (SO_4^{2-}). Showed a positive correlation to PO_4^{3-} and NO_3^- and a negative correlation to Cl^- whereas for the rainy season showed a negative correlation to PO_4^{3-} , NO_3^- and Cl^- .

Violin Plot

Figure 6. Violin Plot for Nonmetallic Minerals element of Lake Nwaebere (water) Dry Season.

Violin plots with inserted box plots serve as essential tools for visualizing and analyzing the analyzed nonmetallic mineral elements concentrations in lakes. They facilitate the understanding of the distribution, variability, and central tendency of elements, which is crucial for evaluating pollution levels and potential risks to the lake ecosystem.

Violin Plot

Figure 7. Violin Plot for Nonmetallic Minerals element of Lake Nwaebere (water) Rainy Season.

Violin plots provide a more comprehensive perspective on data distribution than simple isolated box plots. They integrate the characteristics of a box plot with a kernel density plot, displaying the summary statistics of the data (median, quartiles) in conjunction with the probability density, which highlights possible peaks or clusters within the data. This in-depth perspective is especially beneficial for detecting multiple modes or atypical distributions of nonmetallic elements concentrations in the lake.

Violin Plot

Figure 8. Violin Plot for Nonmetallic Minerals element of Lake Nwaebere (soil) Dry Season.

Violin Plot

Figure 9. Violin Plot for Nonmetallic Minerals element of Lake Nwaebere (soil) Dry Season.

In these cases, the violin plots showed a wide, flat distribution for a nonmetallic element suggesting a widespread contamination for PO_4^{3-} , NO_3^- , with a narrow, peaked distribution might indicate a more localized source for Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} .

Table 3. PCA of nonmetallic Minerals element of the lake Nwaebere: for water and sol.

Water								
	Dry season				Rainy season			
Parameter	PC ₁	PC ₂	PC ₃	PC ₄	PC ₁	PC ₂	PC ₃	PC ₄
Eigenvalue	2.254	1.5061	0.2325	0.00743	2.2249	1.7076	0.06674	0.00075
% of Variance	56.3496	37.653	5.8117	0.1857	55.6228	42.69	1.6686	0.01865
Cumulative (%)	56.3496	94.0026	99.8143	100	55.6228	98.3128	99.9814	100
Soil								
	Dry season				Rainy season			
Parameter	PC ₁	PC ₂	PC ₃	PC ₄	PC ₁	PC ₂	PC ₃	PC ₄
Eigenvalue	1.8258	1.5226	0.5625	0.08908	2.403	1.1121	0.4846	0.00023
% of Variance	45.6456	38.0659	14.0614	2.2271	60.0761	27.8021	12.1161	0.00571
Cumulative (%)	45.6456	83.7115	97.7729	100	60.0761	87.8782	99.9943	100

Principal component analysis (PCA) was performed to further identify the sources of nonmetallic elements in the water of the lake and soil around the lake. In Table 3 nonmetallic Minerals element of the lake Nwaebere (water) in dry season, PC1 had the primary loadings and contributed 56.34% of total variance while PC2 contributed 37.653 % of the total variance. The third PC contributed 5.8117% of the total variance while the fourth PC contributed 0.1857% with the following Eigenvalues of 2.254, 1.5061, 0.2325 and 0.00743 corresponding to PC₁, PC₂, PC₃ and PC₄ However in rainy season, PC1 had the primary loadings and contributed 55.62% of total variance while PC2 contributed 42.68 % of the total variance. The third PC contributed 1.67% of the total variance while the fourth PC contributed 0.02% with the following Eigenvalues of 2.2249, 1.7076, 0.06674 and 0.00075 corresponding to PC₁, PC₂, PC₃ and PC₄ as presented in Table 3. For nonmetallic Minerals element of the lake Nwaebere (soil) in dry season, PC1 had the primary loadings and contributed 45.65% of total variance while PC2 contributed 38.06 % of the total variance. The third PC contributed 14.06% of the total variance while the fourth PC contributed 2.23% with the following Eigenvalues of 1.8258, 1.5226, 0.5625 and 0.08908 corresponding to PC₁, PC₂, PC₃ and PC₄ also as presented in Table 3. For nonmetallic Minerals element of the lake Nwaebere (soil) in rainy season, PC1 had the primary loadings and contributed 60.0761% of total variance while PC2 contributed 27.8021%

of the total variance. The third PC contributed 12.1161% of the total variance while the fourth PC contributed 0.00571% with the following Eigenvalues of 2.403, 1.1121, 0.4846 and 0.00023 corresponding to PC₁, PC₂, PC₃ and PC₄.

Table 4. The correlation matrix in water.

Water								
	Dry season				Rainy season			
Group	Cl ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	NO ₃ ⁻	PO ₄ ³⁻	Cl ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	NO ₃ ⁻	PO ₄ ³⁻
Cl ⁻	1	0.1934	0.9584	0.00236	1	0.9484	0.0694	-0.12
SO ₄ ²⁻	0.1934	1	0.4153	0.7489	0.9484	1	-0.1766	-0.2956
NO ₃ ⁻	0.9584	0.4153	1	0.1104	0.0694	-0.1766	1	0.9476
PO ₄ ³⁻	0.00236	0.7489	0.1104	1	-0.12	-0.2956	0.9476	1
Soil								
	Dry season				Rainy season			
Group	Cl ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	NO ₃ ⁻	PO ₄ ³⁻	Cl ⁻	SO ₄ ²⁻	NO ₃ ⁻	PO ₄ ³⁻
Cl ⁻	1	0.4271	0.2027	-0.509	1	-0.4343	0.6009	0.3292
SO ₄ ²⁻	0.4271	1	0.2824	-0.2788	-0.4343	1	-0.2497	-0.0482
NO ₃ ⁻	0.2027	0.2824	1	0.5901	0.6009	-0.2497	1	0.9489
PO ₄ ³⁻	-0.509	-0.2788	0.5901	1	0.3292	-0.0482	0.9489	1

For nonmetallic Minerals element of the lake Nwaebere (water) in dry season, strong positive correlation was observed between Cl⁻ and NO₃⁻ as well as between SO₄²⁻ and PO₄³⁻ while weak positive correlation existed between Cl⁻ and SO₄²⁻ and Cl⁻ and PO₄³⁻ as well as between NO₃⁻ and PO₄³⁻ as presented in Table 4. For nonmetallic minerals element of the lake Nwaebere (water) in rainy season, strong positive correlation was observed between Cl⁻ and SO₄²⁻ as well as between NO₃⁻ and PO₄³⁻ while weak negative correlation existed between Cl⁻ and PO₄³⁻ and SO₄²⁻ and PO₄³⁻ as well as between N and SO₄²⁻. In the lake Nwaebere (water) in rainy season, strong positive correlation was observed between Cl⁻ and SO₄²⁻ while weak positive correlation existed Cl⁻ and NO₃⁻ and weak negative correlation existed between Cl⁻ and PO₄³⁻ as well as between Cl⁻ and PO₄³⁻. For soil in dry season, medium, weak positive and weak negative correlation was observed between the elements discovered while for rainy season, a strong positive correlation was observed between PO₄³⁻ and NO₃⁻ while weak positive correlation existed Cl⁻ and PO₄³⁻ and weak negative correlation existed between SO₄²⁻ and Cl⁻, NO₃⁻ and PO₄³⁻.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of nonmetallic elements in water and soil within Nwaebere Lake and its surrounding areas revealed varying concentrations of key elements that play significant roles in environmental quality and ecosystem health. The results indicate that while some elements fall within permissible limits for water and soil quality standards, others exhibit elevated levels that may be linked to natural geological processes and anthropogenic activities such as agriculture, domestic waste discharge, and small-scale industrial operations around the lake. Overall, the findings highlight the potential for ecological and human health implications, especially where elevated concentrations may affect water potability, soil fertility, and aquatic life sustainability. Continuous monitoring, coupled with improved waste management practices and pollution control measures, is therefore recommended to maintain the ecological integrity of Nwaebere Lake and safeguard the health of surrounding communities.

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